

HELICAL Open Research Guidelines

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1. Introduction

European researchers have made leading contributions to the large genomic, transcriptomic and clinical datasets from patients with chronic diseases. As part of the HELICAL programme, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 813545, Early Stage Researchers (ESRs) have conducted an analysis of large datasets, using autoimmune vasculitis as a paradigm, through the application of informatics to these datasets in order to gain new biological insights.

Figure 1: HELICAL partner sites' locations

The ESRs process and derive (i.e. use and generate) research data and metadata as well as software and relevant algorithms as part of their projects. Research data includes comprehensive biological and clinical datasets collected from patients with a rare condition. For example, data about the location, age, sex and images showing the kidney tissue of a patient. Research metadata consists of dataset descriptors together with information about the origin and processing of the data. The software describes the routines conducted during the data processing.

Given the particular sensitive nature of the research data gathered, the researchers have proceeded, where appropriate and possible, to pseudonymise the datasets in order to be in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR) as well as other national data protection laws and regulations. Further clarification on whether all ESRs have access to this type of data, whether sites have pseudonymised the data or some datasets have been anonymised is required.

The aim of the HELICAL Open Research Guidelines document is to present a set of recommendations and step-by-step instructions to help ESRs and experts share their findings (whether aggregated data, software or algorithms) as open as possible in accordance with the relevant data protection rules and legislation.

More specifically, the Guidelines aim to provide an understanding and exemplification as to how research findings (data and analysis) can be published securely in an open-access manner. Further details as to the content of the Guidelines is described in the sections below.

2. Objectives

The following section describes the objectives to allow ESRs to publish their data in an open access manner.

2.1. Assembling HELICAL data types

A Google Docs spreadsheet is used to gather information about the data types used in each of the ESR projects. This approach promotes the understanding for the overall HELICAL data types as well as the specifics for each ESR.

Progress against the objective

The ESRs recorded the data type used in their individual projects as a Google Docs spreadsheet shared internally for project use. A copy of the spreadsheet is included in **Annex 1**. The spreadsheet provides columns for demographic, clinical, biomarkers, genetic, experimental and environmental data with appropriate subcategories for a better understanding of the data types. In addition, the spreadsheet was extended to include a data analysis column reporting the methods and data combinations used, a publish data and code column to detail the requirements for each ESR in publishing and a data example column simplifying the understanding of the data used by the ESR. The spreadsheet information was then reviewed by Maria (ESR15), Bahareh (ESR3), Filippo (ESR9) and Albert (ESR1) to validate the imputed information for each ESR. The validation process involved arranging individual calls with the ESRs to clarify and complete their inputs in the Google Docs spreadsheet.

2.2. Identifying EU platform to publish HELICAL data

Identifying a EU platform to publish HELICAL data which is used, generated or gathered from the ESRs would facilitate, guide and enhance the publication data process for the project.

Progress against the objective

The Open Research Europe platform¹ was identified as the most appropriate platform to publish HELICAL data. The EU platform “allows Horizon 2020 beneficiaries to comply

¹European Commission, Directorate-General for DG RTD, ‘Open Research Europe’ open access publishing platform. Available at: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

with the open access terms of their funding” which would offer the ESRs a venue to share their results and insights in a rapid and compliant manner which would enable open, constructive research discussion. Through a reading of the eligibility criteria, the HELICAL project has been identified to meet the threshold for publishing in the Open Research Europe platform. Furthermore, publication costs are covered by the European Commission waiving the fees for the HELICAL project. The platform has an extended documentation section providing guidelines to publish data from a practitioner perspective².

2.3. Designing guidelines for HELICAL ESRs to publish their data

The guidelines are a series of steps to support the ESRs in publishing their data in the Open Research Europe platform.

Progress against the objective

An initial guideline for the ESRs has been designed by the authors of this document. The guideline comprises the steps from identifying existing literature examples with similar research to deposit the data in the Open Research Europe platform. Furthermore, the guideline encourages the ESRs to check standard terms used for their data variables facilitating data reuse within the HELICAL Work Packages (WPs).

The consensus regarding the terms for each WP will be reviewed by a WP representative. In addition, Maria (part of WP4) will support in addressing any queries on data protection issues arising from the datasets and analysis methods, and the code licence questions which may arise from working alongside industry ESRs, thereby facilitating the comprehension of the guidelines for the researchers.

²Ibid, Data Guidelines. Accessed on 1st March 2022. Available at: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/data-guidelines>

3. The Guidelines

A draft guideline was designed by the authors after meeting every two weeks for an online meeting for the 6 months. The draft guideline to facilitate publishing data on an open access repository for the ESRs is structured as (i) a set of prerequisites that need to be met prior to proceeding to publication and (ii) a series of steps to assist in open data publication.

3.1. Open data prerequisites

Prerequisite 1: Gaining/Granting Permissions

When making data available as open data in an open access repository, it is presumed that the processing conducted and datasets used have already been approved as compliant by your institute, company, data owner and/or HELICAL's Data Protection Officer (DPO).³ In this context it is important to note that (1) *gaining* permission to use data and (2) *granting* permission to another to access that data are two very different concepts.

Gaining permission to use the data

ESRs should have already conducted a Data Protection Impact Assessment ('DPIA') providing information as to the legal basis, processing activities (e.g. data analysis, software used, data havens) or sufficient permission that has been granted to the relevant data custodian (e.g. registry and/or databank)⁴ by the data subject⁵ (in this instance a patient or person with a rare condition) to access and use the data. Further information as to the drafting of a DPIA were provided during the delivery of Modules 2 and 3 'Ethical linking of electronic health data to research data to support research, Open Science and uphold FAIR principles'. The Module documents are included on Basecamp and the tailored HELICAL DPIA template can be found in **Annex 2**. The following diagram in Figure 2 exemplifies the overall way the data flow beginning from the patient and ending with the researcher.

³In accordance with the legal basis under the GDPR, accompanying recitals, guidelines issued by the European Data Protection Board and other data protection laws and regulations.

⁴The term 'custodian' is not defined under the GDPR but refers to someone that has administrative control of a document or electronic file. The closest defined term under the GDPR would be that of a "data controller" as defined under Art. 4(7).

⁵A data subject, as per Art. 4(1) GDPR, refers to "an identified or identifiable natural person".

Figure 2: Diagram of data flow

Granting permission to use the data

Publishing the data as open data equates to granting permission for the public to access and use the data themselves. Therefore in order for this to be permissible, **the data subject needs to have consented to their data being published, and the data controller should have been granted the relevant permission to pass on and publish the data in an open access repository.** The ESRs should be aware of the relevant permissions and reflect these in the project's DPIA if they would like to move to publication of the data as Open Data.

The ESRs in this regard should consider: (i) whether the legal basis or permission covers all of the data which will be published as part of the project; or (ii) whether this applies only to parts of the dataset. If the latter, the ESR should create a subset or an example⁶ from the data that can be published as open data.

Given that the majority of ESRs use 'personal data' which can be considered as 'sensitive' (according to the definitions in Articles 6 and 9 of GDPR), these already would be protected through means of anonymisation or pseudonymisation⁷. However, the rare disease nature of the data presents an obstacle for the anonymisation process. Effective anonymisation might not be possible without losing value for research due to the low sample sizes and specialised type of the data (e.g. genomic, genetic and image data). **Each ESR is responsible for providing enough information to the data controller and DPO for them to assess if the data or which data is ready to be published as open data.** Further guidance on anonymisation can be found in the materials and recording of the sessions given as part of the delivery of Modules 2 and 3 of the ESR HELICAL training in June 2020 available on Basecamp.

⁶Example data means simulated data which follows the same structure as the real data for reproducibility.

⁷Some ESRs will collect new personal data during their data collection process. In this case, they should receive approval by an Ethics Committee and be able to make the dataset anonymous prior to publication.

When the data is ready for publication as open data, **data will be accompanied with sufficient research metadata so other researchers can reuse it in different contexts**. In addition, the metadata used in the HELICAL project should use common vocabularies to guarantee collaboration within the consortium. In particular, **metadata should include** a detailed explanation of the following fields: data variables (e.g. name, definition and units), dataset descriptors (e.g. title, publisher and licence), processing purpose, origin and processing of the data (e.g. datasets used and statistical methods applied), hereafter data provenance and lineage.

In addition, if ESRs have permission to publish the data in an open access repository, they need to ensure that the data being published meets the FAIR principles. For this to be achieved, the data should meet the four foundational principles—Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability - to the greatest extent possible, as per Article 5 GDPR. **ESRs should be able to provide evidence as to how the FAIR principles have been met and implemented for the research datasets that are to be published**. This will differ based on “the data types, the nature of research (e.g. ethical sensitivities or commercial partners) and the level of existing support for data sharing”⁸. The FAIR principles can be applied to the design stage of the research to facilitate the documentation of the implementation process followed through the updating of the DPIA.

It is stressed that ESRs cannot proceed on the open data pathway if the ‘Gaining/granting permission’ prerequisite is not met.

‘In that context, the implementation of FAIR data needs to go hand-in-hand with the principle that data created by publicly-funded research must be as Open as possible and as closed as necessary.

The FAIR principles - and related concepts and policies - should be applied not just to data, but to metadata, identifiers, software and Data Management Plans (DMPs) that enable data to be FAIR.’

- European Commission, ‘Final Report and Action Plan from the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data: Turning FAIR into Reality’, Directorate-General Research and Innovation, 2018

⁸European Commission, Final Report and Action Plan from the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data, ‘Turning FAIR into Reality’ Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2018. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf

Prerequisite 2: Ensure Traceability

ESRs should keep a track record of the processing steps applied to the initial data input. The documentation for the processing steps **should include** the timeframe, the data controllers and processors, and the data lifecycle (ordered annotated amendments with the corresponding version, data analysis steps, data combinations, aggregates and subsets) conducted on the data.

Sufficient metadata (as defined in *Prerequisite 1*), included in the dataset publication, can cover most of the processing steps documented. However, we encourage the ESRs to provide notebooks (e.g. Jupyter notebooks or Markdown reports) for the data analysis conducted at the time of publication.

This is a mentality that the ESRs need to keep in mind from the beginning of obtaining the data to the point of publication. We note that this documentation should also reflect any steps applied prior to the initial data input. This in return demonstrates a culture of traceability for other researchers to make trustworthy valid inferences from the published data.

It is stressed that ERSs cannot proceed on the open data pathway if the 'Ensure Traceability' prerequisite is not met.

3.2. Steps towards publication

Step 1: Record data type used in the Google Doc spreadsheet

The ESRs are responsible for recording the data type used in their individual projects as represented in the provided Google Doc spreadsheet. The recording of all data types would support the scientific workflow of the ESRs providing the datasets used in intermediate steps. Once this is finalised, this will require confirmation by the individual supervisors of each project and each change or amendment will need to be reflected in the individual DPIA by the ESRs.

Step 2: Provide an example representing the data collection and analysis processes

Each ESR is tasked with researching and providing an example from literature, which would match their individual project and utilisation of data, algorithm and/or software. This example has already been published in an open access manner to clarify visually the type of data that is used. By means of example, the following footnote provides a notebook describing the data analysis steps followed for an aspect of the project conducted by ESR6. A copy of this can be found under **Annex 3** and at the following link:

- Alejandro Fontal. (2022). helical-itn/data-usage-examples: 0.0.1 (v0.0.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6340349>

Step 3: Agree on a standard data vocabulary

Having had initial discussions with the ESRs and by reviewing the populated Google Doc spreadsheet, inconsistencies in the naming of terms representing seemingly either highly similar or identical values are named differently in each project.

In order to ensure consistency, and to create a consensus in every WP, the creation of a common understanding about what each of those terms correspond to and the creation of a common or standard data dictionary for the variables used by the ESRs in each WP should be established. To achieve this the WPs representatives will communicate with the remaining ESRs and through discussion will come to an understanding and agreement as to what the variables in every project in their WP represent and put together a standard data dictionary. Researchers should ensure that a standard data dictionary has not been already agreed to.

Step 4: Consult existing guidelines from individual research sites

Every university, company and research institute has access to the guidelines concerning the data sharing of their research data and analysis. ESRs should research for, identify and communicate the guidelines to the HELICAL Open Research Guidelines team, composed by the authors Maria and Albert. The team will then review the Guidelines to ensure that any subsequent steps or suggestions included in the document are in line. The Guidelines should be accessible to the ESRs and should already be reflected in their DPIAs. The ESRs must make sure that there is a consensus on the content of these internal guidelines and the Information Governance Policy of the HELICAL project, accessible through Basecamp. A copy of the policy can be found under **Annex 4**.

Step 5: Familiarise with the FAIR data principles

All ESRs need to become familiar with the FAIR principles in order to ensure that their projects are compliant. In this regard, the ESRs have been provided with various educational materials for this purpose as well as throughout the course of the HELICAL project. Examples of these include:

- I. The materials shared and presented during the delivery of Module 2 in April 2020, specifically sessions 4 and 5 - materials of which are stored under the Training folder of the Full Consortium file, accessible on Basecamp.

II. The FAIR data principles⁹ and the FAIRy tale¹⁰ from Zenodo.

III. The open data platform article¹¹ and data guidelines.¹²

Step 6: Publish research data in a open data repository

We recommend publishing your research data in the open data repository preferred by each community. Different communities might prefer one repository from another based on the flexibility of the licence, the fields in the description, the collaboration with particular journals, the user interface or the data upload limit per publication. Researchers not clear on how to choose the data repository preferred by the community can check nature data repositories¹³ and re3data¹⁴ to inform their decision.

However, we wanted to share a general go to open data repository to have a starting point:

Zenodo – <https://zenodo.org/> and Github – <https://github.com/>

Zenodo allows researchers to publish data in any size and format, which addresses the diverse data types and formats within the project (e.g. clinical data, environmental data, image biopsies or questionnaire data). In addition, researchers can describe their data so it is easier to reuse by others, which can then be linked to related research (e.g. journal publications). When publishing the data in Zenodo, the content will automatically obtain a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), making the content citable and discoverable.

The ESRs can link their publication with the ITN HELICAL community to have a central repository to access HELICAL open source artefacts. The steps to link the publication are the following: (1) log in to your Zenodo account, (2) choose the publication to link, (3) click on edit (top right corner), (4) select ITN HELICAL Community, (5) save and publish. The linkage request will then be approved by the curator of the community.

Github cloud-based hosting service that allows developers and researchers to store, manage their code, while tracking the changes to their code during the developing process. Furthermore, Github code can be linked to Zenodo which will generate a DOI for the code, making it citable. Below there are two examples of data and code published by ESR1 in Zenodo and Github:

⁹Zenodo, Principles. Accessed September 2021. Available at: <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>

¹⁰Zenodo, A FAIRy tale. Accessed September 2021. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/2248200#.YG85UBLTVhG>

¹¹ Zenodo, Guidelines for authors. Accessed September 2021. Available at: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/article-guidelines/>

¹² Ut supra 8. Available at: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/data-guidelines>

¹³ <https://www.nature.com/sdata/policies/repositories>

¹⁴ <https://www.re3data.org/>

1. Navarro-Gallinad, Albert. (2021). Environmental data associated to particular health events example dataset (20211012T120000) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5823426>
2. Albert Navarro-Gallinad. (2021). navarral/serdif-api: Release version 1.0.1 (v1.0.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5776245>

However, prior to publishing the data accompanied with metadata and code to Zenodo and Github, the ESRs must get approval from their supervisors, the HELICAL team and the data owner that it can be published.

4. Acknowledgements

Thank you to all the ESRs for their help in aiding the collection of the required information to draft these guidelines and for providing their DPIAs in order for the present document to correctly reflect the steps followed in practice.

Particular thanks to Bahareh Kosravi and Filippo Guerri in their participation and contributions during the first meetings that were held in late 2020 to coordinate efforts as well as for their help in reviewing and organising the information inserted in the Excel spreadsheet containing the data used by the ESRs in the project.

5. Annexes

The Guideline will include an annex to track the publication process for data, code and workflows for the ESRs. The annex will be structured with the steps from the presented guidelines.

Annex 1: HELICAL ESR data types

Annex 2: HELICAL tailored DPIA

Annex 3: Exemplary notebook describing data analysis steps

Annex 4: HELICAL Information Governance Policy